

Fresh weight of azolla from insecticide-treated and untreated plots at Sanpahtawng Rice Experiment Station, Cheingmai, Thailand.

months February-May (see figure). Severe insect damage and high summer temperatures caused yields in treated plots to be lower than 6 t/ha. At San-

pahtawng and Sakolnakorn azolla was attacked mostly by a webworm. The key pest at Ubolratchatani was the caseworm. *h*

Changing trends of insect pests of rice in Manipur

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During the past 8-9 years several new insect pests have begun to harm rice in Manipur. Some are spreading to new areas and some that were minor pests are now major pests. Changing trends and their possible causes are discussed below.

Rice leaf butterfly *Melanitis leda ismene*, reported in 1973 in the central district, now infests several high yielding and local varieties in five other hill districts in the state. The pest is more abundant in wetland rainfed conditions where water supply is more or less assured. However, it also infests several local paddy varieties grown in shifting cultivation in dryland rainfed conditions.

The slug caterpillar *Latoia [=Parasa] bicolor* was first noticed in 1980 in cooler regions of East District, Ukhrul. Primary areas of infestation are Kamjong and Phungyar subdivisions, where

several local varieties are monocropped in shifting cultivation in rainfed dryland conditions. The insect is a voracious leaf feeder. It has not been found in other rice belts of the state.

Rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* was first found in the warmer Jiribam subdivision adjoining Silchar district of Assam. In 1972, it appeared in cooler areas of Chingai in East District, Ukhrul. By 1973 the pest had reached the central valley of Imphal where 200 acres of paddy grown in rainfed transplanted wetland conditions were infested. The pest is most dominant in Imphal West-I and West-II subdivisions where several high yielding varieties and local varieties are grown.

Rice thrips *Baliothrips biformis* attacked large areas of nursery and transplanted paddy at Sowumbung and Sagolmang in Imphal East subdivision in 1975 kharif. It has also been observed in Tengnoupal. Rice fields are susceptible at early tillering stage during long dry spells. Plants grown in dry, poor soils are most often attacked.

Rice leaf miner (prob. *Pseudona-*

pomyza asiatica) was observed in 1973 in the cold area of Mao in the north district. A local dryland variety grown on terraced rainfed fields at an altitude of about 2,000 m was affected. Until 1979 the pest was unknown in other rice growing areas of Manipur. In 1980 it attacked local variety Phouren during early tillering stage at Shamurou in Imphal West-II.

Rice bug *Leptocorisa acuta* is occasionally a serious pest of first crop paddy (Mar-Apr to Jun-Jul) and causes minor damage to the second crop (Jul-Aug to Nov-Dec). The insect is more active in warm, humid conditions at flowering to dough stage. Low temperature at flowering stage during the second crop does not favor insect multiplication.

Rice hairy caterpillar *Psalis pennatula* has been an important rice pest for only 2-3 years. In a few pockets of Tengnoupal district a heavy infestation, sometimes 10-15 caterpillars/hill of Moirang-phou, occurred in July 1982 and caused complete plant defoliation. Sporadic caterpillar infestations are reported during the early monsoon rains.

Changing insect pest trends may be caused by changing cultivation patterns and new agricultural strategies. The area planted to high yielding varieties has increased from 12,000 ha in 1973 to 72,530 ha in 1982. Similarly, the area of minor irrigation in the state increased from 1,700 ha in 1973 to 45,000 ha in 1982. Consumption of NPK rose from 1,820 t in 1973 to 3,000 t in 1982. *h*

Effect of meteorological factors on oviposition and nymphal hatching of, rice tungro virus vector *Nephotettix virescens*

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The effect of meteorological factors on oviposition and nymphal hatching of *Nephotettix virescens*, a vector of rice tungro virus, was studied in the net-house for 2 years. Seeds of Taichung Native 1, Jaya, and IR20 were sown and transplanted in earthen pots at monthly

intervals. Fifteen plants of each cultivar were grown in insect-proof cages measuring 60 × 60 × 40 cm. Four plants were used for oviposition and four for nymphal hatching. Twenty 10-day-old *N. virescens* females were released in each cage, then removed after 24 hours. Four days later, half of the plants were dissected and eggs were counted under a microscope. Cultivars in the remaining cages were observed daily for 15 days and the emerging nymphs were counted.

Maximum temperature range was 27 to 37°C, minimum temperature ranged from 12 to 26°C, relative humidity varied from 60 to 87%, daily rainfall range was 0.0 to 15.5 mm, and sunshine varied from 3.4 to 9.9 hours.

Varietal preference for oviposition differed little. The number of eggs and nymphs per leafhopper was greater during monsoon season (July-October) than in winter (November-February) and summer (March-June) seasons (Table 1). Monthly data show there are oviposition/hatching peaks in September and March. The September peak was largest.

Table 1. Reproduction of *Nephotettix virescens* over 3 seasons on 3 rice varieties, Cuttack, India.

Season	Eggs (no./female)			Nymphs (no./female)		
	TN1	Jaya	IR20	TN1	Jaya	IR20
Winter (Nov-Feb)	4.1	3.4	4.1	2.0	2.0	2.5
Summer (Mar-Jun)	2.9	3.4	3.5	1.3	1.4	1.7
Monsoon (Jul-Oct)	7.1	6.9	7.4	3.1	3.0	3.2

Table 2. Relationship between meteorological factors and eggs and nymphs of *Nephotettix virescens*, Cuttack, India.^a

Meteorological factor	Correlation coefficients					
	Eggs			Nymphs		
	TN1	Jaya	IR20	TN1	Jaya	IR20
Relative humidity	0.5725**	0.5165**	0.5450**	0.5268**	0.4902*	0.2886
Rainfall	0.4753*	0.4173*	0.4805*	0.2455	0.2547	0.2979
Sunshine hours	-0.4922*	-0.4240*	-0.5137*	-0.2714	-0.2487	-0.2402

^a*Significant at P = 0.05, **significant at P = 0.01.

The number of eggs in all the cultivars was positively correlated with relative humidity and rainfall and negatively with hours of sunshine. Number of nymphs was positively correlated with relative humidity in Taichung Native 1 and Jaya (Table 2). This relationship indicates that relative humidity is more important in oviposition and nymphal

hatching. No temperature correlation was found.

Seasonal and monthly data indicated that optimum maximum temperature is 32°C, minimum temperature is 26°C. High relative humidity (84%), low intensity of rainfall, and limited sunshine hours (5.2 h) appeared to encourage oviposition and nymphal hatching. ✎

Life cycle of the green hairy caterpillar and its chemical control

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The green hairy caterpillar (*Noctuidae: Rivula nr. atimeta*) causes serious defoliation at the seedling stage of rice in the Philippines. Its life cycle was examined in artificial infestations in the greenhouse. Pairs of unequal size pupae were clipped to the tillers of 20day-old Taichung Native 1 (TN1) plants. The smaller of each pair was assumed to be male. Mylar cages kept emerging moths on the plants.

Female moths lay single eggs, an average of 128 each, or more than 16-224 per female. Eggs are laid in rows on both sides of a leaf, usually near the tip. The egg is round, 1 mm in diameter, and greenish when freshly laid. Incubation is 3-5 days.

Five larval instars last an average 13.5 days. A full-grown larva is 16 mm long with setae along the length of its body

Green hairy caterpillar (*Rivula nr. atimeta*).

(see figure). Pupation averages 5 days. Preoviposition is 14 days and oviposition averages 3.7 days. The life span is 4.1 days for males, 5.2 days for females.

Nine insecticides were evaluated against the green hairy caterpillar. To determine contact toxicity, compounds were sprayed on third-instar larvae in